

Dermaptera

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Dermaptera, Lower Permian stem-line

Protelytroptera (extinct order)

Apachelytron transversum, Lower Permian, Moravia, Czech Republic

Dermapteran ordinal level wing characters are present in a plesiomorphic state.

Dermaptera stem-line late Permian

† Protelytroptera: *Acosmoelytron delicatum*

Hind wing evolution

Dermaptera stem-line: *Protelytron permianum*

Unfolded HW

Dermaptera: *Forficula auricularia*

(E) Anisolabididae

(F) 'Labiduridae'

(G) Forficulidae

(H) Chelisoichidae

(I) Spongiphoridae

(A) 'Diplatyidae'

(B) 'Pygidicranidae'

(C) *Allostethus indicum*

(D) Apachyidae

Dermaptera: anal lobe venation

Dermaptera: HW articulation

↑ rare plesiomorphy: humeral plate is visibly composed of F & B-PC and F & B-C

Dermaptera: wing base diversity

'Diplatyidae'

'Pygidicranidae',
Echinostoma micropteryx

'Pygidicranidae',
Pyragra fuscata

'Pygidicranidae',
Tagalina burri

Dermaptera: wing base diversity

Important:
"Humeral plate" in Anisolabididae shows its original composition of fused fulcalare (F) and basivenale (B)!

Dermaptera: wing base diversity

Forficulidae

Chelisochidae

Spongiphoridae

In Spongiphoridae PR-Cu shows that it was originally long and narrow, and later divided into two pieces (as shown best in Apachyidae).

HW Dermaptera

Dermaptera hind wings

Dermaptera: fustis with remnants of principal veins. Note that in Eudermaptera (G, H, I) head of fustis is separated from base by groove.

From Haas and Kukalová Peck, 2001, *Dermaptera: structure, folding and...* (2001)

(A) "Diplatyidae"

(F) "Labiduridae"

(B) "Pygidicranidae"

(E) Anisolabididae

(G) Forficulidae

(C) *Allostethus indicum*

(H) Chelisochidae

(D) Apachyidae

(I) Spongiphoridae

Anisolabiidae:
Carcinophora

F. Haas & J. Kukulová-Peck: Dermaptera: Structure, folding and... fig 8

! Rare plesiomorphy:
 In *Anisolabididae*, humeral plate retains original composition of F PC&C and B PC&C !?
 do not reduce

Apachyidae: *Apachyus* sp.

Apachyidae: *Apachyus* sp.

Chelisochoidea: *Chelisoches morior*

Cheliosochidae:
Cheliosoches morior

Chelisochidae: *Chelisodes morior*

Protelytroptera: L. Permian, Moravia
 Dermapteran Stem Line: *Apachelytron transversum*

(A) 'Diplatyidae'

(B) 'Pygidicranidae'

(C) *Allostethus indicum*

(D) Apachyidae

(E) Anisolabididae

Dermaptera: *Forficula auricularia*

Forficulidae: *Allodahlia* sp.

HW Forficulidae: *Allodahlia*

BM reduced

Forficulidae: *Forficula auricularia*

Forficulidae
Forficula auricularia
HW

HW Forficulidae: *Forficula auriculata*

Forficulidae: new, very large

Ecuador

Philadelphia Academy of Science

fulcalare M is reduced!

(A) 'Labiduridae'

(B) Forficulidae

(C) Chelisochidae

(A) 'Labiduridae'

(B) Forficulidae

(C) Spongiphoridae

(D) Chelisochidae

HW Labiduridae: *Labidura riparia*

(A) 'Labiduridae'

(B) Forficulidae

(C) Chelisochidae

HW Labiduridae: *Labidura riparia*

this fold placed more distad than in Diptera
same as transverse fold anterior of AP in Diptera
CuA, M, R fields compressed

HW Labiduridae: *Labidura riparia*

Labiduridae: *Labidura riparia*

Also as in Mantodea: base of Cu is disconnected from basivenale,
and similar folding lines in anojugal lobe

Labiduridae: *Labidura riparia*

HW

PR PC probably reduced

Sparatta pulchra

New family?

Pennsylvania Academy of Science

(probably a new fam. between Pygid. and Labid...

Pygidicranidae *Echinosoma*

Australia

Pygidicranidae

Echinosoma

Australia

Cassis

au Lapo: CuA 3+4 gone
CuA 1+2 shortened
JP stem gone

Spongiophoridae: *Marava arachidis*

Spongiophoridae: *Marava arachidis*

Spongiophoridae (? or new family) *Sparatta pulchra*

Spongiphoridae

(A) Spongiphoridae

HW Springiophoridae: *Marava arachidis*

